

The Open Balkans: Tangled Up in Disbelief and Aspirations

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Introduction

The region of South-East Europe, and particularly the Western Balkans, have intermittently had various intra-regional initiatives throughout its modern history, which either neighboring countries or external actors have received with skepticism. Being situated in the periphery of Europe, at the “borderland of empires” (Lampe & Jackson, 1982; Lampe & Mazower, 2006), the interaction between the nation-states of the Balkans and Europe has been fraught with ambiguity. On the one hand, the liberal institutions and norms of Western Europe have been considered a model for progressive elites in the region (Mishkova, 1994; Daskalov & Mishkova, 2014), albeit not successfully rooted and institutionalized in the Balkans. On the other hand, the Balkans have been depicted and imagined (Todorova, 1997) primarily as a region that is under-developed, prone to conflict and nationalism, and in need of external intervention, if not custody, by great powers to reduce the “civilizational divide.” Henceforth, the relationship between the Western Balkans and the global society, represented by Europe and the North-Atlantic community, has shunned or discouraged autonomous regional initiatives and policies from this area of South-East Europe.

The Open Balkans initiative, which the Republic of Serbia, Albania and North Macedonia established in 2019, is one of those political initiatives stemming from an intra-regional endeavor, which other Western Balkans states that are not yet part of this initiative, and to some extent, the EU and the U.S, have met with skepticism. Thus, despite the normative commitment to the so-called four freedoms, similar to the single market as a corollary of economic integration in the European Union, and the usual mantra of economic growth and development articulated in the public deliberations and official proclamations of the Open Balkans initiative, support for this locally rooted initiative has not increased. Although the skepticism towards the Open Balkans may appear sound and justified, paradoxically the individual national-state policy of individual, merit-based integration into the European Union has hampered the Western Balkan region from exerting its political agency in a globalized society.

Rather than simply relying on the ideas and stances of the representatives of the Western Balkan governments as well as the official positions of other influential external actions, and taking them at face value, this report aims to provide reasons for the emergence, limitations and faltering of the Open Balkans intra-regional initiative. The inclusion and references to the public deliberations and position-takings on the Open Balkans, which the individual country reports meticulously and extensively provide, will be considered as the empirical background of the analysis in this report. The

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most common and relevant questions and quandaries that are raised by the Open Balkan initiative, as indicated in the individual country reports on the Open Balkans relate to the added value of this intra-regional initiative of regional cooperation among the paraphernalia of similar ones, and whether the Open Balkans can foster peacebuilding in the region as well as complement the integration of the region into the European Union. To understand the functioning, the opportunities, and the ways through which the faltering of and skepticism on the Open Balkans initiative can be rectified, the report will address the effect of the EU leverage in the Western Balkans in contrast with other external actors, as well as highlight the political and economic conditions of the polities in the region, which underpin the Open Balkans initiative's impact.

EU leverage in the Western Balkans and the OB as an alternative to EU integration

The EU leverage in the Western Balkans polities does not seem to exert the expected influence to countervail what scholars term as the “Western Balkans’ fatigue towards the EU” (Belloni, 2016) after the stalling of the EU enlargement, nor induce changes in the Western Balkans’ polities by bringing them closer to liberal democratic regimes and a competitive market economy. Inadvertently, a weakened EU leverage and normative power concerning the Western Balkans has led the EU institutions and influential member states such as Germany and France to devise EU policies and strategies to maintain the commitment to a prospective European future for the Western Balkans. It is precisely the absence of a coherent vision of what the European perspective of the Western Balkans looks like that constitutes the quandary and the opportunity for Western Balkan governments, EU representatives and other external actors to not just mess with the status quo.

Civil society organizations and the regional think tank epistemic community when addressing the EU integration of the Western Balkans emphasize the shifting ground of the EU enlargement policy. “The EU policy towards Western Balkans with the manifold challenges in that region ... reveal cracks both within internal EU policy, institutional design and the European identity” (Kirchner et al., 2021, p.12). Albeit the EU Commission’s recognition of the importance of geopolitics as an imperative, if not a coherent framework, for shaping the EU policy towards the Western Balkans (Kirchner et al., 2021, p. 8), the diverse overlapping strategies to cope with the Western Balkans continue to persist. Adding to the existing regional cooperation initiatives such as the Regional Cooperation Council (RCC), South-East Cooperation Initiative (SECI) and the Central European Free Trade Agreement (CEFTA), Germany initiated the Berlin Process initiative. Further along the way, France together with the Netherlands convinced other members of the European Council and the EU Commission to make the EU enlargement process more accountable and yet more complex for aspiring EU candidate countries of the Western Balkans (Tilev et al., 2021, p. 6). Highlighting the “Fundamentals First” cluster of the new mechanism of the EU enlargement, which centers on the rule of law would, ideally, be beneficial to the effectiveness of Western Balkan polities, yet the same mechanism may as well become “a new more powerful tool in the hands of the Member states, to ensure the protection of their collective (and national) strategic interests” (Tilev et al., 2021, p. 14). Under conditions of “inconsistent application of the EU conditionality” (Richter & Wunch, 2020, p. 6) and “the simultaneous attempts to stabilize and democratize” (Richter & Wunch, 2020, p. 6) the EU has reduced its asymmetric leverage in Europeanizing the Western Balkan polities. Henceforth, contradictory or overlapping EU strategies about the Western Balkans, which most likely could make “differentiated integration become the default option for officials in Brussels” (Belloni & Brunazzo, 2017, p. 35), bearing in mind as well the European Political Community (EPoC) project initiated recently by France, enable intra-regional initiatives such as the Open Balkans to take hold in the political imagination of the Western Balkan power elite.

In her detailed report on the OB initiative from the perspective and perceptions of the Republic of Serbia, Jelica Minić argues that the lack of a coherent EU enlargement strategy for the Western Balkans can make the Open Balkan initiative an intra-regional mechanism that enhances economic cooperation and thus indirectly contributes to the EU accession. Simonida Kacarska and Stefan Ristovski emphasize in their country report for North Macedonia that although the political actors remain divided about the priority that needs to be assigned to the Open Balkan as an alternative to other regional initiatives, especially those established by important EU member states, the official position of the North Macedonian government is that “the Open Balkans and the EU accession are not mutually exclusive alternatives.” The official stance of the North Macedonian government seems to indicate that the Open Balkans is a dress rehearsal for a similar yet more complex EU single market. Thus, the Open Balkans initiative becomes an antechamber to the EU integration and a mechanism of social learning for the citizens and governments of the Western Balkans. The proponents of the initiative, at least on the level of normative commitments and understanding of the EU integration process, while not relinquishing their aim to become members of the European Union, by intending to replicate the EU model at the regional level could gauge how adaptive and effective their domestic institutions are in sustaining this replication at a smaller scale and scope of institutional complexity. At the very least, the Open Balkans initiative may be successful in its “pedagogical effect” meaning that it enforces the commitment to integrate their economies and societies into the EU. It is a different matter to what extent the Open Balkans could achieve and stabilize a differentiated integration of the Western Balkans without the prospect of EU accession.

Countries of the Western Balkans that have refrained from officially participating in the Open Balkans initiative seem to justify their skepticism using political and economic reasons. In the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina, as Nedžma Džananović emphasizes, the stances in favor or against the Open Balkans initiative reflect the political divisions in the country between representatives of the Republika Srpska entity and those representing the Federation of BiH. Without renouncing the relevance of regional cooperation and aiming towards the perspective of EU membership, the representatives of the Federation of BiH claim that “further integration would lead to the renewal of the modified ‘Yugosphere.’” (Džananović, 2022). The same division across political loyalties and cleavages is present in Montenegro concerning the stances on the Open Balkans. Discussing whether the OB is an alternative to the EU integration, Marko Pejović argues that under conditions of a dynamic and complex EU enlargement policy and were the Open Balkans to replicate the Berlin Process goals, this intra-regional initiative would become an alternative to the EU integration. On the other hand, Kosovan representatives in the political and civil sphere, according to the report written by Sylë Ukshini and Valdrin Ukshini, would have been more in favor of a sustainable Open Balkans initiative were the normalization of relations between Kosovo and Serbia taken center stage. According to them, economic cooperation should not proceed with normalization and peacebuilding in the region. Yet, it seems that the existence of the Open Balkans initiative has made countries skeptical of this endeavor more in favor of the Berlin Process than before.

Due to the absence of a coherent EU enlargement policy and the emergence of competing or contradictory individual initiatives by EU member states such as the recent project of the European Political Community (EPoC), the Open Balkans initiative, despite the entrenchment of existing divisions among the countries of the Western Balkans as a consequence of the OB, may remain attractive to some countries in the region unless incorporated into a wider regional initiative guided by the influential EU member states, as it is the case of the Berlin Process. As the sections below will explain, due to the nature of the political regimes that dominate in the region and the configuration of the power elite, coupled with a weak dominance of the rule of law, the Open Balkans initiative, as it is envisioned right now, can hardly replicate the EU model of economic integration. Nonetheless, this initiative brings to the fore a more assertive Western Balkans region in terms of intra-regional

initiative instead of band-wagoning, as much as it does reinforce existing divisions in the region. As Arjan Dyrmishi, director of the Center for the Study of Democracy, highlights in his semi-structured interview with the AIIS, one of the advantages of the Open Balkans initiative is that “it focuses the attention to regional problems, at a geopolitical level, because not all the international actors have the same degree of awareness and attention to the problems of the Western Balkans” (October 2022).

External Actors and the Open Balkans

In the last decade, non-Western external actors, and great powers such as China and Russia have increased their influence in the Western Balkans. One of the reasons for this happening is the transformation of the international order “as a new ‘age of hybridity’ with no overriding set of paradigms to shape global governance” (Öniş & Kutlay, 2020, p. 2). What is usually known as the “Beijing consensus” is “an alternative to neoliberalism influences” (Öniş & Kutlay, 2020 p. 2) and is characterized by a “highly personalized network of capital accumulation and state-permeated corporate relations” (Öniş & Kutlay, 2020, p. 3). The actual challenge of the Beijing consensus in the Western Balkans is the lack of political conditions attached to the economic model and bearing in mind the competitive authoritarian regimes of the Western Balkans, it “[leads] credence to the notion that successful capitalist transformation can be accomplished in a highly authoritarian political environment” (2020, p. 4). As Anastas Vangeli terms it, “China’s charm offensive” (2021, p. 10) has lured some Western Balkan governments to cooperate with Chinese state firms to build “highways, power plants, and restoring industrial capacities” (Vangeli, 2021, p. 10). Although having a minor role in the regional trade with the Western Balkans, “accounting for roughly 6 percent of the regional trade” (Shopov, 2021), China has invested heavily in infrastructure in the region such as the investment in the construction of the Bar-Boljare highway in Montenegro, the Tuzla power plant in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the steel industry and telecommunications in Serbia (Shopov, 2021).

The energy sector, infrastructure, and digital technology appear to be the key sectors of the economy of the Western Balkans. The Chinese “Beijing consensus” model is competing with the EU strategy of connectivity and the energy market via the Berlin Process. The Open Balkans initiative, which is to some extent strictly an economic endeavor to actualize the so-called four freedoms in the Western Balkans, does not have a unified strategy or policy concerning these strategic sectors of the national and regional economy. The configuration of the power elite in Western Balkan hybrid regimes and the status of the Western Balkan economies as “transitional economies” (Vangeli, 2021, p. 12) and “not faring well under Wester-led globalization” (2021, p. 12) transforms the economic influence of China into a “personal project of [Western Balkan] ruling elites” (Vangeli, 2021, p. 11). The U.S. and the European Union have urged the Western Balkan countries to be cautious not to enhance the influence of China in the region. Nonetheless, “... the persistent development gap between the Western Balkans and the EU” (Shopov, 2021) is a structural condition that allows for an increased influence of non-Western external actors in the region. In this respect, the Open Balkans initiative, despite its lack of “clarity on the concept” (Ukshini & Ukshini, 2021) and the absence of a “single document that defines its scope of actions” (Ristovski, 2022, p. 6), aims to implement, within certain limitations, EU models of economic integration. Thus, if it does not have an effective role in building a regional market, it does have a normative or ideological role in using the EU parlance and practices for economic growth and integration. On the other hand, the inclusion of the already existing memoranda of the Open Balkan initiative on the recognition of university diplomas, certain professional licenses and cross-border movement through IDs¹ in the recent Berlin Process summit of November 2022

1 <https://europeanwesternbalkans.com/2022/11/03/berlin-process-western-balkans-leaders-sign-agreements-on-increased-mobility/>

indicates that the Open Balkans is amenable to inclusion in the EU's larger regional cooperation initiatives and not just an alternative to the EU integration.

Besides China, particularly in the context of the unprovoked and illegal invasion of Ukraine by Russia, the Russian Federation is one of the external powers that does have a considerable influence on the Western Balkan region. For some reason, either traditional or economic countries in the Western Balkans have close ties with Russia. For one, "Russia exercises leverage over Serbian politics and wants to see Serbia as their foreign policy ally" (Nelaeva & Semonov, 2016, p. 57). On the other hand, Serbia is "dependent on energy supplies and investments from Russia" (Nelaeva & Semonov, 2016, p. 59). The public support that Sergei Lavrov lent to the Open Balkans initiative, amid the war in Ukraine, created fierce criticisms from even representatives of the states that are in favor of the Open Balkans by blocking the airspace for his visit to Serbia.² In this respect, the involvement of Russia, albeit diplomatically, in support of this intra-regional initiative, which remains non-inclusive, challenges the credibility of the commitments towards an assertive and self-integrated region. It may also unintentionally reinforce the existing skepticism on the Open Balkans among countries such as Kosovo, Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Russia, as Paul Stronski argues, "[by] bolstering grassroots anti-Western sentiment and corrupt vested interests across the Balkans, makes the region's governance shortcomings more acute and damages the domestic reforms that are a prerequisite for further integration into Euro-Atlantic economic, political, and security structures" (Stronski, 2022).

Experts and civil society representatives interviewed in the individual reports on the Open Balkan initiative express their consternation towards the contradictions of the Open Balkans seen from strictly electoral or domestic interest. As Zoran Panović mentioned, the idea of conflating the Open Balkans initiative with the "Serbian World" as two complementary projects is quite inappropriate and contradictory (Minić, 2022). This conflation seems to indicate that the interpretations of the importance of the Open Balkans initiative, by political representatives and domestic actors in countries in favor of the initiative, weakens the inclusive potential of the Open Balkans and its initial European vocation, by accommodating non-Western sponsorship of this initiative rhetorically or diplomatically. Simonida Kacarska and Stefan Ristovski (2022, p. 19) identify frictions among the countries that support the Open Balkans initiative regarding the expected EU alignment that each member of the initiative should manifest. "The non-alignment of Serbia with the EU sanctions policy and more broadly its foreign policy remains a stumbling block in terms of achieving stronger political impact ...". According to the North Macedonian position, founding members of this initiative and non-Western external actors should not challenge the European orientation of the Open Balkans initiative. Ilir Kalemaj highlights that one of the drawbacks of the Open Balkans that have propelled other Western Balkans states towards "skepticism is Serbia's membership in the Russian-led Eurasian Union" (2022, p. 2). In fact, in the context of the "age of hybridity" of the global order, when the Western Balkan countries "have developed a lesser sense of agency in dealing with global politics" (Vangeli, 2021, p. 4), with diverse traditions regarding relations with external actors, and usually accustomed to "be monitored and controlled by the external actors" (Đukanović, 2022 cited in Minić 2022, p. 6), mainly the EU or the U.S., the ambiguities of the Open Balkans initiative become apparent as long as its ambitious remain not only economic.

² https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/short_news/varhelyi-to-attend-open-balkan-meeting-amid-claims-of-russian-backing/

An Intra-regional Single Market and the Western Balkans Power Elite

One of the highlighted goals of the Open Balkans initiative stated in the Joint Statement of the leaders of the Open Balkans in July 2021 is “to have a single market, without borders.”³ Such an ambitious goal of the Open Balkans initiative, resembling the single market established in the European Union that took decades of incremental changes, trial and error, and inclusive negotiations, is assumed to occur rather swiftly and despite the dominance of hybrid regimes and informal networks in the Western Balkan countries. Henceforth, for the achievement of a regional market not to remain just a lofty goal, it would require a more conducive institutional setting for a sustainable regional economic integration as well as the inclusion of other states such as Montenegro, Kosovo and Bosnia and Herzegovina as well. On the other hand, even if this were the shared aim of all the countries of the Western Balkans, “the integration in the global market” (Pula, 2014, p. 511) of the founding members of the Open Balkans initiative and those not participating in it is rather different. States such as Serbia, Bosnia and North Macedonia, according to Pula, “are most integrated with global markets (p. 512), while the most dependent economies in the Western Balkans include Albania, Kosovo and Montenegro, which are dependent particularly on imports or financial FDI inflows (p. 512). Hence, it is difficult to assume and expect “economic uniformity in the region” (Pula, 2014, p. 513). Moreover, “EMU members [as they] are the primary trading and investment partners of individual Western Balkan states” (Pula, 2014, p. 510).

The non-inclusive dimension of the Open Balkan initiative for the time being apart from overlapping with existing regional market institutions such as the Common Regional Market (CRM), or the Regional Economic Area (REA) established at the Trieste Summit in 2017, seems to be skewed in terms of its trade flows. According to the 2019 data on trade, the countries that have established the Open Balkan initiative have higher exports in non-Open Balkan countries than among themselves (Ristovski, 2022, p. 15). In more concrete terms, “North Macedonia, Albania, and Serbia exports are higher in non-OB countries than in OB participating countries, 56.37%, 72.82% and 72.26% of the intra-regional export value respectively” (Ristovski, 2022, p. 15). Ristovski argues that intra-regional trade would not benefit OB members or non-participants given the status of the Open Balkans initiative (Ristovski, 2022, p. 15). Along the same lines, Zef Preçi, Executive Director of the Albanian Center for Economic Research, mentions in his interview that: “The Open Balkans cannot be considered as a proper economic initiative that would increase trade flows or investments among the Western Balkan countries because it remains an isolated initiative of Serbia and Albania (joined later by North Macedonia)” (October 2022).

There has been some slight improvement in the trade flows between the members of the Open Balkans based mostly on previously existing trade patterns. As Simonida Kacarska and Stefan Ristovski (2022) emphasize, for North Macedonia “... the trade with both Serbia and Albania continued to grow in the next years, with the exception of the pandemic 2020” (p. 13) after the Open Balkans was established. Ilir Kalemaj underlines that despite the sectoral agreements about the four freedoms that the founding members of the OB have signed, “most of these agreements are either dealt with in the past in other frameworks such as CEFTA ... or too slow to move things fast forward” (2022, p. 9). Consequently, the Open Balkans has slightly improved the existing pattern of trade among the founding members of the initiative. According to Nedžma Džananović, most of the experts consider that “the Belgrade-Pristina relation has affected CEFTA, and had it reflected on BiH...warn[ing] of the great probability that the issue of Belgrade-Pristina relations would remain unresolved within the OB” (2022, p. 9). Authors of the report on the Kosovan perspective regarding the Open Balkans express their skepticism about whether the intention of establishing a single market would function

3 <https://vlada.mk/node/26063?ln=en-gb>

properly and be sustainable given the exclusion of other Western Balkan states, such as Kosovo, which may be considered more as “a trade transit zone” (Ukshini & Ukshini, 2022, p. 4) rather than “an entity with attributes of a sovereign country” (2022, p. 4). A constant feature of the arguments presented by the representatives and experts of non-participant states of the Open Balkans is that economic cooperation and integration cannot be sustainable if it takes priority over the resolution of political disputes among the Western Balkan states, such as the lack of reciprocal recognition of Serbia and Kosovo, as highlighted by Arian Starova, ex-Minister of Foreign Affairs of Albania (October 2022).

Besides the limitations and partial advantages of the Open Balkans initiative concerning the goal of an intra-regional single market, as mentioned above, it is important to highlight the political and domestic context that undergirds this initiative. Some of the drawbacks of the Open Balkans, such as not addressing the presence of an informal economy in the Western Balkans or not founding the intra-regional institutionalization of the Open Balkans on the EU Single Market *acquis* (Ristovski, 2022) stem from a certain configuration of the state-society relations, degree of effectiveness of political institutions and ultimately of the composition of the power elite in the Western Balkan polities. There is a growing shared consensus among political scientists and experts on the Western Balkans that these societies are characterized by electoral authoritarian regimes, state capture and patronage politics (Richter & Wunsch, 2020; Keil, 2018; Bieber, 2018; Lavrič & Bieber, 2020; Kapidžić, 2020), a pattern that seems to be reinforced due to the EU’s dilemma in favor of stability instead of democracy in the region (Smith et al. 2020).

Contrary to the expectations that economic growth and social transformation would lead to a differentiation of the elites in Western Balkans and a more pluralistic society, the recent developments in the region despite limited democratization processes turned out to be reversed into competitive authoritarian regimes (Bieber, 2018), show that the prevailing elite configuration is that of “the coalescent power structure or power elite” (Engelstad, 2018, p. 440). This means that there is no clear differentiation between the political elite and economic elite in the Western Balkan societies and that they constitute an “intricate set of overlapping cliques [that] share decisions having ... national consequence” (Mills, 1956, p. 9). Thus, the most appropriate understanding of the notion of elites relates, particularly due to “the political and economic structure” (Mills, 1956, p. 96) of the societies in the Western Balkan, to “[those] with the possession of decisive political power that gives them disproportionate influence on political and social outcomes” (Engelstad, 2018, p. 440). The establishment of the Open Balkans and the aim to model the intra-regional economic integration according to the EU takes place precisely under these social and political conditions that underlie the dominant characteristics of state-society relations in the Western Balkans. As Solveig Richter and Natasha Wunsch emphasize that the “pressure for liberalization in the absence of a comprehensive legal framework allowed a small economic elite to realize private gains and build powerful networks that influence decision-making” (2020, p. 3). According to their argument, the mechanism of political conditionality of the EU has not managed to increase the political accountability of the Western Balkan governments and did not function as a bulwark to the process of state capture that “entrenched informal networks” (2020, p. 3) of the power elite dominate. “Most of the political processes and dynamics in the Western Balkans are characterized by “the rise of strong leaders, who have focused on re-building the political system so that it suits their – and their party’s – interests” (Keil, 2018, p. 4). Therefore, in the absence of the rule of law, and efficient market institutions domestically, the Open Balkans’ goals of intra-regional economic, or political integration would falter and most likely reflect a patchwork of diverse exclusive interests of the power elite.

The Open Balkans as a Peace Project?

Albeit there is no direct reference in the joint declarations or memoranda signed by the founding members of the Open Balkans initiative, the public rhetoric of heads of the governments seems to imply that this intra-regional endeavor contributes in the long run or indirectly to a more peaceful co-existence in the Western Balkans. Yet this remains a far-fetched claim under conditions of truncated intra-regional cooperation within the Open Balkans due to the absence of states such as Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo, which violence, war and dismembering of the social fabric and local communities deeply marked. One of the reasons for claiming such an advantageous outcome of the Open Balkans stems from the assumption that economic cooperation and integration in certain sectors of the economy lead to further mutual interdependence and that states involved in economic integration become reluctant to wage war. Yet, there is a divide across the Western Balkan countries, which is mentioned in most of the country reports on the Open Balkans that were produced for this project. The founding members of the Open Balkans do not have bilateral disputes with each other. Notwithstanding the stability and cooperation between the Republic of Serbia, Albania and North Macedonia, bilateral disputes and a lack of proper normalization of relations exist between individual members of the Open Balkans and the non-participant countries in the Western Balkans. Thus, it becomes less likely that a truncated economic integration between existing members of the Open Balkans could vindicate the effect of a market economy as one of the “key tenets of the liberal peace” (Belloni, 2020, p. 84). For one, that would require the inclusion of all the states of the Western Balkans into the Open Balkans as a necessary precondition yet not a sufficient one to assess the effects of intra-regional economic integration in bringing sustainable peace in the region. Secondly, transforming the Open Balkans into a genuine peace project of the Western Balkans, as modeled around the post-war reconstruction of Europe and the signing of the France-West Germany friendship treaty, would require addressing the normalization of relations between Kosovo and the Republic of Serbia. Therefore, if realizing a sustainable peace in the Western Balkans through the means of the Open Balkans is a shared goal, the intra-regional integrative mechanisms of the Open Balkans, and the very initiative needs to be rethought, by becoming more inclusive, cooperative, and pluralistic. Political imagination to avoid the limitations of the standard top-down imposition of peacebuilding by international peacebuilding agencies, as well as recognition of past atrocities would be the necessary tools for a reinvigoration of an intra-regional process of normalization of relations, reconciliation, and peacebuilding among the Western Balkan states. The way the Open Balkans initiative operates and the fact the most prevailing political regime in the Western Balkans is the hybrid political regime reduces the likelihood of the Open Balkans having a tangible effect in resolving bilateral disputes or constituting an indigenous process of sustaining peace in the region.

Conclusion

It would be rather easy to dismiss the Open Balkans initiative as irrelevant due to its overlap with several existing regional initiatives. External actors and international agencies established most of these initiatives. On the other hand, it is not quite rational to portray the Open Balkans as a mere instrument of power politics in the region, without putting sufficient effort and resources into enhancing and reshaping the initial intra-regional initiative first, as prospective members of the Open Balkans. Recognizing the limitations of the Open Balkans such as the absence of elaborate foundational documents, permanent coordinating structures and units, as well as its inherent contradictions between rhetorical commitment to European norms and practices and the actual implementation and design of sectoral cooperation or integration in the intra-regional economy, could function as a

basis for making the Open Balkans more inclusive and a stable intra-regional initiative as reiterated in almost all of the country reports.

Regardless of whether the Open Balkans remains an adamant exclusive initiative of three founding members such as Serbia, Albania and North Macedonia, paradoxically deepening the differentiation and divide within the Western Balkan countries or becoming accommodative to the preferences of the non-participant states, this initiative has placed the Western Balkans at the center of attention of relevant external actors such as the European Union and the United States. Finding strategies and policies to respond to or incorporate some of the goals of the Open Balkans initiative, such as the re-ignition of the Berlin Process and the U.S. policy to encourage the Open Balkans as an inclusive intra-regional economic integration mechanism shows that this initiative could provoke a counter-movement due to the exercise of an assertive intra-regional policy of less liberal states.

Probably the project of the Open Balkans would have been inconceivable if the process of the EU enlargement of the Western Balkans had not been complex, to some extent incoherent in sustaining the commitments for the accession of the Western Balkans, and less indicative of various competing strategies and mechanisms instead of full membership. On the other hand, the ushering of the international order into an age of hybridity had increased the leverage of non-Western external actors. A restricted power elite dependent on informal networks and patronage, if not state capture, characterizes the presence of competitive authoritarian regimes in the Western Balkans and weakens the effectiveness of the Open Balkans initiative.

References

- Belloni, R. (2016). The European Union blowback? Euroscepticism and its consequences in the Western Balkans. *Journal of Intervention and State-building*, 10(4), 530-547. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17502977.2016.1211387>
- Belloni, R. (2020). *The rise and fall of peacebuilding in the Balkans*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Belloni, R., & Brunazzo, M. (2017). After Brexit: The Western Balkans in the waiting room. *European Review of International Studies*, 4(1), 21-38. <https://doi.org/10.3224/eris.v4i1.02>
- Bieber, F. (2018). Patterns of competitive authoritarianism in the Western Balkans. *East European Politics*, 34(3), 337-354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21599165.2018.1490272>
- Daskalov, R., & Mishkova, D. (Eds.). (2014). *Entangled histories of the Balkans: Transfers of political ideologies and institutions*. Brill.
- Džananović, N. (2022). “Open Balkans” and Bosnia and Herzegovina: New opportunity for even more divisions. Albanian Institute for International Studies, Tirana.
- Engelstad, F. (2018). Models of elite integration. In H. Best & J. Higley (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of political elites* (pp. 439-457). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Kacarska, S., & Ristovski, S. (2022). *The Open Balkans initiative: The view from North Macedonia*. European Policy Institute, Skopje.
- Kalemaj, I. (2022). *Open Balkans: An Albanian Perspective*. Albanian Institute for International Studies, Tirana.
- Kapidžić, D. (2020). The rise of illiberal politics in Southeast Europe. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 20(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2020.1709701>
- Keil, S. (2018). The business of state capture and the rise of authoritarianism in Kosovo, Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia. *Southeastern Europe*, 42(1), 59-82. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18763332-04201004>

- Kirchner, M. J., Lopandić, D., Ćerimagić, A. (2021). *The Conference on the future of Europe: How could Visegrád be the voice for the Western Balkans?* Institute for Democracy “Societas Civilis” – Skopje.
- Lampe, J.R., & Jackson, M.R. (1982). *Balkan economic history 1550-1950: From imperial borderlands to developing nations*. Indiana University Press.
- Lampe, J. R., & Mazower, M. (Eds.). (2006). *Ideologies and national identities: The case of twentieth-century Southeastern Europe*. Central European University Press.
- Lavrić, M., & Bieber, F. (2021). Shifts in support for authoritarianism and democracy in the Western Balkans. *Problems of Post-communism*, 68(1), 17-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10758216.2020.1757468>
- Mills, C.W. (1956). *The power elite*. Oxford University Press.
- Minić, J. (2022). *Open Balkan beyond the noise of controversy – regional cooperation analysis and the way forward: A view from Serbia*. Albanian Institute for International Studies, Tirana.
- Mishkova, D. (1994). Modernization and political elites in the Balkans before the First World War. *East European Politics and Societies: and Cultures*, 9(1), 63-89. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0888325495009001005>
- Nelaeva, G., & Semenov, A. (2016). EU-Russia rivalry in the Balkans: Linkage, leverage, and competition (The case of Serbia). *Romanian Journal of European Affairs*, 16(3), 56-71.
- Öniş, Z., & Kutlay, M. (2020). The new age of hybridity and clash of norms: China, BRICS, and challenges of global governance in a postliberal international order. *Alternatives: Global, Local, Political*, 45(3), 123-142. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0304375420921086>
- Pejović, M. (2022). *Open Balkans and Montenegro*. Albanian Institute for International Studies, Tirana.
- Pula, B. (2014). Effects of the European financial and economic crisis in Kosovo and the Balkans: Modes of integration and transmission belts of crisis in the “super-periphery.” *East European Politics*, 30(4), 507-525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21599165.2014.937430>
- Richter, S., & Wunch, N. (2020). Money, power, glory: The linkages between the EU conditionality and state capture in the Western Balkans. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 27(1), 41-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2019.1578815>
- Ristovski, S. (2022). *Comparison of the Open Balkan and the Common Regional Market: What's new for the regional economic integration in the Western Balkans?* European Policy Institute- Skopje.
- Shopov, V. (2021). *Decade of patience: How China became a power in the Western Balkans*. European Council on Foreign Relations.
- Smith, N.S., Khaze-Markovic, N., & Kovacevic, M. (2021). The EU's stability-democracy dilemma in the context of the problematic accession of the Western Balkan states. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 29(2), 169-183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14782804.2020.1823823>
- Stroński, P. (2022). *Russia in the Balkans after Ukraine: A troubling actor*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace.
- Tilev, D., Nechev, Z., Međak, V., Ćela, A., Emini, D., Džananović, N., Mumin, N., & Gjeta, A. (2021). *The European Union new methodology and its long-term impact on accession negotiations*. Institute for Democracy “Societas Civilis” – Skopje.
- Todorova, M. (1997). *Imagining the Balkans*. Oxford University Press.
- Ukshini, S., & Ukshini, V. (2022). *Open Balkan and Kosovo*. Albanian Institute for International Studies, Tirana.
- Vangeli, A. (2021). *China's ideational impact in the Western Balkans 2009-2019*. Prague Security Studies Institute.